

Aerosols produced during biomass conversion and their organic extracts – cytotoxic and oxidative response of a lung cell model system

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Abstract

Residual products from the rural economy are increasingly utilized in practice as biofuels. However, the safe application of the resulting combustion-generated ultrafine particles warrants toxicological studies, including cytotoxicity and oxidative stress, as well as alternative methodologies such as genetic methods.

The aim of this work was to formulate a methodological workflow to study the cytotoxic and oxidative stress responses of human A549 cells, originating from human lung tissue, exposed to particulate matter (PM) in the submicron range (UPM). The study focused mostly on cherry stone and wheat straw combustion products, taking into consideration the influence of the sample collection approach.

The assays for cell viability, protein carbonyls, and HMOX1 expression by RT-qPCR showed minimal cytotoxic effects and a concentration-dependent increase in oxidative stress markers. Notably, elevated HMOX1 expression indicated the presence of an antioxidant response, which was stronger with cherry stone UPM compared to UPM from wheat straw. The sample collection protocol only marginally influenced biological outcomes.

This study represents an innovative and alternative animal-free workflow, well suited for the toxicological assessment of combustion-generated UPM. It showed weaker cellular responses to wheat straw UPM compared to cherry stone UPM. This approach could well be applied for assessing the health risks of exposure to other ambient air pollutants.

Keywords

HO-1, HMOX1, oxidative stress, RT-qPCR, A549 cells, ultrafine particulate matter, biomass combustion

Introduction

Biomass residues from agriculture, forests, and the food industry are used for various purposes. Agricultural production is mainly used for human and animal consumption but also as a raw material for biofuel production. Residues from the food industry, such as fruit stones after fruit processing, together with other types of biomass residues, could be intended for conversion into solid biofuel or, in some cases, can be directly burned (Petrova et al. 2023). Biomass is one of the most widely used alternative fuels, which is considered to have significant energy potential with low net CO₂ emissions. Several main challenges limit its widespread use, including the environmental impact in areas where many households using biomass/solid biofuels are concentrated, as well as challenges with the economic sustainability of its use for energy needs (Suman and Gautam 2018; Azam et al. 2020).

The secondary by-products of the incomplete combustion of fossil and alternative renewable biofuels are particulate matter (PM) and its organic constituents, mainly polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). They exhibit diverse toxic effects on organismal tissues, organs, and systems, which, upon prolonged exposure, could cause permanent health deterioration (Obernberger et al. 2006; Warnatz et al. 2006). In soot, the predominant compositional component is PM with a size of less than one micron (Adánez-Rubio et al. 2020; Ferreira et al. 2021). These particles are considered ultrafine particulate matter (UPM) (Gao and Wu 2011).

There is insufficient information on the chemical composition of PM and UPM generated from the combustion of biofuels of different origins. It is predominantly the chemical composition that is responsible for the harmful effects on human health. Assessing the toxic effects of these key pollutants is essential for public health worldwide (Dimbareva et al. 2023).

According to the latest WHO data from 2019, air pollution is responsible for a large share of deaths due to disease, mainly of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems. Examples of such diseases are ischemic heart disease, stroke, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and lung cancer (World Health Organization 2025). Among the main factors involved in the pathogenesis of the listed diseases, local and systemic inflammatory processes, as well as oxidative stress, play a major role.

In the last decade, emphasis has been placed on the application of alternative *in vitro* and *in silico* methods for the assessment of the toxicity of chemicals, with the aim of using existing information and limiting the use of experimental animals. One such approach is the identification of basic changes in the expression of genes and proteins as markers for assessing oxidative stress resulting from exposure to toxic substances. An example of such a biomarker for assessing oxidative stress is the presence of carbonylated proteins due to oxidative damage. The cellular defense system against oxidative stress is composed of a subset of antioxidant proteins. Heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1) is a microsomal enzyme that is induced in response to cellular stress and diverse oxidative stimuli. HO-1 can reduce oxidative stress, attenuate inflammatory responses, and lower the rate of apoptosis (Zhu et al.

2017). Thus, the expression of the gene HMOX1, responsible for the synthesis of HO-1, is another early marker of cellular exposure to oxidative challenges. This enzyme is one of the few inducible molecules that can protect the lungs from increased oxidative stress. HO-1 degrades heme to carbon monoxide, free iron, and biliverdin, the latter being further degraded to bilirubin, which has antioxidant properties (Araujo et al. 2012). HO-1 is induced in response to oxidative stressors. Low concentrations of carbon monoxide have been shown to exert cyto- and tissue-protective effects, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative, and anti-apoptotic effects, as a result of HO-1 expression (Ryter et al. 2007). HO-1 is expressed by airway epithelial cells, alveolar macrophages, and bronchial epithelial and inflammatory cells. At the cellular level, it is predominantly located in the endoplasmic reticulum, although it has also been reported to be present in mitochondria, the cell nucleus, and the plasma membrane (Slebos et al. 2007). Many factors induce HO-1 expression, such as hyper- and hypoxia, glutathione depletion, cytokines, lipopolysaccharides, and oxidative stress. Overexpression of HO-1 has been experimentally shown to protect cells from hyperoxia *in vitro*. The protective role of HO-1 has been demonstrated *in vivo* in hyperoxic lung injury in rats (Hu et al. 2013). It also protects against oxidative stress in the lungs of rats immunologically challenged with LPS (Laurent 2006). Other studies confirm the innate and adaptive immunomodulatory capacity of HO-1 in several models of LPS-induced acute lung injury, in which HO-1 decreases polymorphonuclear leukocyte migration to the lung, thereby reducing the extent of oxidative tissue damage (Lee et al. 2020).

A major challenge of *in vitro* studies of combustion products is the generation of a reproducible and precise dosing method, which would allow adequate comparisons between the safety of different combustion materials. This has been addressed in previously published studies by lyophilizing particulate matter before redispersion in cell culture medium (Çakmak et al. 2019). For example, the uncertainty over whether the use of inert substances as lubricant on collector discs in impactors could affect the biological responses in *in vitro* cellular studies needs to be addressed.

The present study aims to evaluate the cytotoxic response and oxidative stress state of human lung cell culture A549 exposed to the influence of particulate matter (PM) $\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ in aerodynamic diameter, as well as to test whether the use of lubricant during the step of sample preparation in the impactor affects *in vitro* testing.

Materials and methods

Materials

A549 cells were obtained from the European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures (ECACC, Cat. No. 86012804). Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), fetal bovine serum (FBS), L-glutamine, trypsin, and Bradford's reagent were obtained from Sigma Chemical Co. (Germany). The Protein Carbonyl Content Assay Kit (Cat. No. ab126287)

was obtained from Abcam Ltd. (United Kingdom). iScript™ Select cDNA Synthesis Kit (Cat. No. 1708897) and SsoAdvanced™ Universal SYBR® Green Supermix were obtained from Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc. (USA). RNeasy Mini Kit (Cat. No. 74104) was obtained from QIAGEN (Germany).

Biomass/solid biofuel pellet generation and analysis

In previous studies conducted at the National Centre for Public Health and Analysis (NCPHA, Sofia), in collaboration with a research team from the Technical University of Sofia, quantitative analysis of 16 priority polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons was performed by gas chromatographic analysis of five types of biomass/pellets (wheat straw, cherry stones, sunflower, coffee, and lucerne), obtained mainly as waste products from agriculture or the food industry (Naydenova et al. 2020). The biomass samples were burnt under model conditions using a controlled method in the laboratory (Naydenova et al. 2023) through a horizontal tube reactor with a 14-stage cascade impactor for collecting particles in a wide range (from 0.015 µm to 10 µm).

After chemical analyses, two types of biomass (wheat straw and cherry stones) were selected for cytotoxicity testing with the MTT assay and the HMOX1 gene expression assay by quantitative real-time reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR).

Cell culture

The A549 cell line originates from human adenocarcinoma alveolar basal epithelial cells. The cell culture was maintained in high-glucose DMEM and supplemented with FBS and L-glutamine in a humidified incubator at 37 °C and 5% CO₂.

Sample preparation for *in vitro* studies

Ten milligrams of each particulate matter sample were dispersed in 10 ml of distilled water upon sonication, followed by rapid freezing at –80 °C and lyophilization. The resulting powder was kept at –80 °C, then weighed and redispersed in culture medium containing 1% FBS at a concentration of 500 µg/ml immediately before treatment of cells. A series of dispersions with descending concentrations (200, 100, 50, 20, 10, 5 µg/ml) were obtained by dilution with culture media. Culture media in the 96-well plate were exchanged with aliquots of the resulting dispersions, or with culture media only for the negative control, and culture media containing 1 mM H₂O₂ for the positive control.

Cell viability assay

The MTT assay was applied to evaluate the effects of particulate matter on the viability of A549 cells (Mosmann 1983). In order to assess the effects of treatment upon cells, cells were plated in 96-well plates at a cell density of 10⁴ cells/well and allowed to attach overnight before experimental treatment. After 24 h, each well was carefully aspirated and

exchanged with MTT solution in fresh cell culture medium. Upon incubation for 2 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂, the contents of the wells were exchanged with dimethyl sulfoxide and incubated in a place protected from light for 15 min. Absorbance was measured at 570 nm with a background read at 690 nm, which was subtracted in order to eliminate the influence of non-specific obstacles to light. Viability results were expressed as a percentage of control values.

Protein oxidation assay

In order to assess the effects of treatment upon cellular protein oxidation, we measured the amount of protein carbonyls. The assay is based on the reaction of DNPH with protein carbonyls. DNP hydrazones formed in this reaction are easily quantifiable at 375 nm absorbance (Levine et al. 1990). 5 × 10⁵ A549 cells/well were plated in 6-well plates and allowed to attach overnight. Then, cells were treated for 24 h with test dispersions at 50 µg/ml or 500 µg/ml, or with culture medium for the control. After thoroughly washing the cell layer, protein carbonyl content was quantified using the Abcam Protein Carbonyl Content Assay Kit (Cat. No. ab126287), following the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, protein samples were prepared and incubated with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH) to derivatize carbonyl groups, followed by removal of excess reagent. The resulting DNP-hydrazone products were solubilized and transferred to a 96-well plate for spectrophotometric measurement at 375 nm. Protein concentration in each sample was determined in parallel using Bradford's protein assay, with bovine serum albumin as the standard. Carbonyl content was calculated by normalizing absorbance values to protein concentration, using a standard curve generated with known concentrations of bovine serum albumin, and background absorbance was subtracted from all readings.

Gene expression by quantitative real-time reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR)

Total RNA was extracted from A549 cells using the RNeasy Mini Kit, Cat. No. 74104 (QIAGEN). The iScript™ Select cDNA Synthesis Kit, Cat. No. 1708897 (Bio-Rad), and the GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 (Applied Biosystems) were used for the first step of PCR. The PCR protocol for cDNA synthesis used the following conditions: 42 °C for 60 min, 85 °C for 5 min. Gene expression was analyzed with the CFX Opus 96 Real-Time PCR system (Bio-Rad) and CFX Maestro software. RT-qPCR was performed with primers for the reference gene β-actin and the target gene *HMOX1*, using SsoAdvanced™ Universal SYBR® Green Supermix (Bio-Rad), under the following cycling conditions: 95 °C for 30 sec, followed by 40 cycles of 95 °C for 15 sec, 54 °C for 20 sec, and 72 °C for 35 sec. The amplification temperature of each gene, melting point, optimal conditions, and reaction specificity were determined. The sequences for SYBR primers (Choi et al. 2014, p. 506) were as follows:

For the reference gene β -actin:

- Forward primer CCCACTCCTAAGGAGGATG;
- Reverse primer AGGGAGACCAAGCCTTCAT.

For the target gene, HMOX1:

- Forward primer CACGCATATACCCGCTACCT;
- Reverse primer CCAGAGTGTTTCATTCGAGA.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were carried out using GraphPad Prism 6 Software (USA). One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's post-test was applied for comparisons among multiple groups and against controls. Simple linear regression was used to evaluate the relationship between variables.

Results and discussion

Sample preparation

One of the challenges with studying particulate matter in *in vitro* systems is the difficulty of generating a homogenous dispersion, which is necessary for precise dosing. Visual inspection (Fig. 1) of the dispersion of combustion materials collected from the impactor with or without lubricant shows that, after ultrasonication and vortexing, the dispersion forms aggregates that sediment within minutes. However, this factor was controlled for by redispersing the treatment media immediately before serial dilutions—and again immediately before pipetting

Figure 1. Photographs of culture medium dispersion of wheat straw or cherry stone combustion biomass collected with (+) or without (-) lubricant. Images are taken one minute after ultrasonication and vortexing.

into cell culture wells—so that the obtained treatment groups were precisely exposed to the predefined doses of particulate matter.

Cytotoxicity assessment by MTT cell viability assay

The MTT assay is the standard assay for evaluating changes in cell viability – an inversely correlated marker of cytotoxicity. We evaluated the effects of two types of UPM from solid fuel exhaust and an additional sample with a different particle-collecting protocol (without lubricant) in order to control for the potential effects of the lubricant, which should be an inert hydrocarbon mixture (Fig. 2). All of the test compounds exerted only marginal cytotoxic effects, which could be considered negligible in the context of the high concentrations applied.

Even at the highest concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, the absorbance value does not drastically drop, although some variability is present—possibly explained by absorbance from the highly concentrated UPM. With cherry stone UPM, the measured effect can still be considered weak cytotoxicity. Nevertheless, it is clear that—despite the slight changes in viability due to the lubricant – wheat straw-derived particulate matter decreases A549 cell viability less compared to cherry stone-derived particulate matter.

Protein oxidation assessment by protein carbonyls content

In order to understand whether the slight changes in viability were accompanied by cellular protein oxidative damage, we carried out the protein carbonylation assay at two concentrations: the highest applied in the viability assay (500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), as well as the moderate 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Fig. 3A). The obtained experimental data were normalized to protein content and showed no statistically significant differences among treatment groups, irrespective of whether the particulate matter was collected with lubricant or not. However, there was a visible trend of increased protein carbonyls at the higher concentrations compared to the moderate ones across all particulate matter types. To interpret the protein carbonylation data, we built a regression curve of the relationship between protein carbonyl

Figure 2. Effects on the viability of A549 cells after treatment with particulate matter from wheat straw (A) or cherry stone (B, C) burning, collected with (A, B) or without (C) lubricant. Viability values are expressed as average \pm SD. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's post test; $p^* < 0.05$, $p^{**} < 0.01$, $p^{***} < 0.001$ vs. ctr.

Figure 3. Effects on protein carbonylation levels (A) of treatment with particulate matter from wheat straw (Wheat) or cherry stone (Cherry) burning, collected with (+) or without (-) lubricant, and correlation between protein carbonyls in A549 cells and cell viability upon oxidative challenge with H_2O_2 (B).

content and cell viability (Fig. 3B). The slope—indicating a decrease in viability with increased protein oxidation—was statistically significant ($p = 0.0012$). With an increase in carbonyl content of 0.01 units, as observed in Fig. 3A, a negligible decrease in cell viability—between 6.2% and 1.9%—could be expected (95% confidence interval of the slope: -619.3 to -186.5).

Oxidative stress assessment by gene expression of HMOX1 (RT-qPCR)

In order to evaluate whether cellular defense mechanisms against oxidative damage were activated differentially upon treatment with the studied types of combustion material dispersions, we studied the relative expression levels of HMOX1 in treated A549 cells.

Normalization is an essential component of a reliable RT-qPCR when the aim is to study gene expression in order to quantify responses to oxidative stress. With the lung-originating cell line A549, exposure to UPM derived from the combustion of cherry stones and wheat straw resulted in increased gene expression of the target gene HMOX1 after treatment with 500 µg/ml of UPM from both types of biomass, compared to the expression of the same gene in untreated controls (red bars in Fig. 4A–C).

Cells treated with UPM from cherry stones had high relative levels of expression of HMOX1 in comparison to the expression quantified in wheat straw-treated cells. This coincides with the presence of weak cytotoxic effects on A549 cells, observed only with cherry stone UPM, whereas with wheat straw UPM such effects were hardly detected. Samples of cherry stone with lubricant had lower relative levels of expression of the HMOX1 gene compared to the samples of cherry stone without it.

Figure 4. The relative expression levels of HMOX1 in A549 cells treated with concentrations of 500 µg/ml (red) and 50 µg/ml (green) of a cherry stone sample, collected with lubricant (A), cherry stone sample, collected without lubricant (B), and wheat straw sample, collected with lubricant (C), are presented as normalized expression ($\Delta\Delta Cq$), relative to the control (untreated cells), using β -actin as a reference gene.

Conclusion

The combustion and thermal degradation of solid fossil and alternative fuels lead to the formation of a large variety of products harmful to the environment and to human health. The proven anti-inflammatory, cytoprotective, and immunomodulatory effects of HO-1 and its catabolic products are functionally significant in the pathogenesis of diverse human diseases, as well as in the early adaptive responses occurring before the onset of cell death. Our study demonstrated that the expression of HMOX1 represents a sensitive biomarker for oxidative stress. Thus, cellular *in vitro* model systems and genetic methods are a suitable alternative tool for assessing the toxic effects of UPM, as they are accessible, reproducible, and do not cause suffering to experimental animals. They allow the tracking of molecular mechanisms of toxicity, such as early changes in gene expression of factors inducible under early stages of oxidative stress. Moreover, our study addressed the use of lubricant during sample collections, which appears to be of limited significance to the outcomes of viability and oxidative stress assays on A549 cells. The application of this workflow in other areas of toxicological risk assessment could provide meaningful information for identifying and reducing health risks—both for the exposure of the general population and for occupational exposure scenarios.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

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The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: A549 cell line, originating from human adenocarcinoma alveolar basal epithelial cells was obtained from the European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures (ECACC, Catalogue No.: 86012804).

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: Tz.G., Y.Y., K.V., I.N., V.Tz. Methodology: Y.Y., K.V., Y.M., I.N., Tz.G. Validation: K.V., Y.Y., Formal analysis: Y.Y., K.V., Y.M., Investigation: K.V., Y.Y., I.N., Resources: I.N., Tz.G., M.K.-B., V.Tz., D.S., Data Curation: Y.Y., K.V., Writing – Original draft: K.V., Y.Y., Tz.G., Writing – Review and Editing: K.V., Y.Y., Tz.G., V.Tz., D.S. Visualization: Y.Y., K.V., Supervision: Tz.G., V.Tz., M.K.-B., Project administration: I.N., Tz.G., V.Tz., M.K.-B., D.S., Funding Acquisition: I.N., Tz.G., V.Tz., M.K.-B., D.S., K.V., Y.Y.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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